

Fracture Detection using Digital image processing and Machine learning

Ajel Varghese John

Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
ajelvarghesejohn2024a@mca.ajce.in

Lisha Varghese

Department.of ComputerApplications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
lishavarghese@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The diagnosis of human fractures through X-ray imaging is essential in medical practice, yet manual interpretation of X-ray images is time-consuming and requires specialized expertise. The challenges posed by the scarcity of experienced radiologists and Orthopedic surgeons, especially in medically underserved regions, necessitate the development of automated fracture identification systems. This research explores the application of digital image processing techniques coupled with machine learning algorithms to automate fracture detection from X-ray images. Specifically, edge detection algorithms, with a focus on the Canny method, are employed to identify relevant boundaries and transitions indicative of fractures. Subsequently, the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) feature extraction technique is utilized to capture discriminative image features. Machine learning classifiers, including Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), and Random Forest (RF), are then employed to classify X-ray images into fractured and non-fractured categories based on the extracted features. The study demonstrates the efficacy of the proposed approach, particularly highlighting the superiority of SVM for bone fracture detection. This automated fracture identification model holds promise for improving diagnostic accuracy and accessibility, particularly in regions facing shortages of skilled medical professionals.

Keywords— Fracture detection, X-ray imaging, Digital image processing, Edge detection, Canny method, Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG), Machine learning, Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), Random Forest (RF), Medical diagnosis, Automated system, Diagnostic accuracy, Accessibility, Python

I. INTRODUCTION

The human body is comprised of 206 bones, varying in size and shape. Bones serve as the primary structural elements of the body, and bone fractures are a prevalent medical issue [1]. Fractures can occur due to stress on a bone or from various diseases. X-ray imaging is a common method used to detect fractures [2]. This technique involves taking an image with an X-ray, which is

then analyzed using image processing methods like edge detection, image enhancement, and segmentation.

This paper focuses on processing x-ray images through the edge detection technique.

Sight is the process through which humans collect and interpret visual information. When a computer performs this task, it is known as digital image processing and analysis. Digital image processing employs computer algorithms to enhance images [3]. It has several advantages over analog image processing, including the production of an improved, high-quality image after processing, depending on the techniques used [4]. As digital image processing evolves, more algorithms are developed, integrating input data [5]. This allows for the prevention of various processing issues, such as noise generation and signal distortion at specific points. The study of digital image processing is growing at an extraordinary pace.

Enhancing the appearance and quality of images is a key aspect of analysis [6]. Image processing is utilized in various fields, including robotics, document processing, logo and symbol recognition, and a wide range of biomedical assessments. Edge detection is a principal focus within image processing, as every image contains boundaries or edges. The objective is to investigate and assess various edge detection methods to identify the most efficient technique for x-ray imaging [7]. Image processing techniques encompass feature extraction, edge detection, classification, acquisition, and filtering. Figure 1 illustrates the process.

Ongoing research in computer-assisted diagnostics aims to enable devices to diagnose patients with high precision and minimal resource usage. Certain systems utilize clinical photographs for immediate patient diagnosis by extracting distinctive features from the images after reducing noise. In newly developed healthcare systems, locating X-ray images is crucial. The identification of bone fractures within an image is considered a critical step, relying on the criteria established to determine if an X-ray image depicts a normal or fractured bone.

The objective of this project is to determine the presence of bone fractures by creating a system that automates fracture diagnosis with the aid of computer-assisted image processing techniques. The process begins with an X-ray image; noise is reduced through filtering, edges are detected, features are then

extracted, and finally, a classification algorithm categorizes the images as either fracture or non-fracture.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

W. Kareem has detailed a technique for image categorization [1]. Myint, Wint, and others have developed a classification method for leg bone fractures with 82% accuracy [2]. Dhirendra Yadav and Sandeep Rathor proposed a deep learning method for X-ray image classification [3]. Meena, Tanushree, and Sudipta Roy introduced a deep supervised method for image categorization [4]. Leonardo Tanzi, Enrico Vezzetti, and their team proposed a deep learning approach for the categorization of femur bone fractures [5]. Kandel, Ibrahim, et al. described a fracture detection system based on transfer learning [6]. Santosha Chandra Rao Karanam, Y. Srinivas, and S. Chakravarty provided an overview of various classification strategies [7]. Koray Açıcı, Emre Sümer, and Salih Beyaz utilized PSO and GA optimization methods for fracture identification [8]. S. Utasa, S. Varada, A. Goel, and others have developed an automatic system for diagnosing neck fractures [9]. Rocky Upadhyay and Prakash Tanwar offer a comprehensive review of various edge detection methods [10]. N. Ohari and N. Singh introduce an edge detection method specifically for fracture detection and assert that this intelligent method is highly effective [11]. Dilshad Ahmed and Roojwan Hawezi provide an in-depth discussion on the techniques of edge detection and feature extraction [12].

K. Farah states in her theory that Leukocytes, commonly known as white blood cells, are crucial components of the immune system utilized by the body to combat infections. These cells are pivotal in the battle against viruses due to their ability to traverse blood vessels and infiltrate infected tissues. The white blood cell count, often manually assessed by healthcare professionals in blood samples, is vital for disease detection because of its diagnostic significance. White blood cells are categorized into five types: basophils, neutrophils, eosinophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes. The focus on automated methods for the identification of blood cell images has intensified recently, particularly with the expansion of the Video Internet of Things (VIoT). The development of machine learning and image processing algorithms for the automated classification of blood cells is the primary objective of this research.

Roojwan Hawezi says Artificial intelligence algorithms have revolutionized various sectors by accurately predicting outcomes through pattern recognition in extensive datasets. In the medical field, AI's predominant application has been in diagnosing imaging problems and predicting therapeutic outcomes. However, the efficacy and limitations of AI in automating fracture detection and classification have not been extensively researched. This systematic study aims to address two main inquiries: the proficiency of AI models in detecting and classifying fractures, as measured by accuracy and the area under the receiver operating characteristic (AUC) curve, and the comparative performance of AI versus human examiners in fracture detection and classification tasks.

A thorough search was conducted in the PubMed, Embase, and Cochrane databases up to September 6, 2018, utilizing keywords related to "fracture," "artificial intelligence," and "detection, prediction, or evaluation." Out of 1221 studies

identified, ten were included in the review. This review adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) guidelines and was registered with PROSPERO (CRD42018110167). The studies documented the accuracy and Area Under the Curve (AUC) of AI models in fracture classification and detection, employing a modified methodologic index for nonrandomized studies (MINORS) to assess quality. The results were promising, with AI demonstrating accuracy between 83% to 98% in seven studies and AUC between 0.95 to 1.0 in five studies, indicating near-perfect prediction capabilities.

In a recent study by Koray Açıcı, the precision of fracture classification by artificial intelligence (AI) was reported to be between 77% and 90%, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.94. Significantly, AI demonstrated performance on par with human evaluators in the detection and categorization of hip and proximal humerus fractures in two separate trials. In another study, AI showed similar accuracy for wrist, hand, and ankle fractures. These preliminary findings suggest that AI holds promise for enhancing diagnostic processes in orthopedic surgery and other medical fields, particularly in fracture detection and classification. However, challenges persist, especially concerning the establishment of reference standards for the testing and training of AI models. Future research should focus on addressing these challenges and regulatory barriers to ensure AI's seamless integration into clinical workflows.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research focuses on developing an automated system specifically for identifying and classifying fractures in X-ray images of the hand, elbow, and shoulder. The traditional method of manual X-ray examination is time-consuming and relies on the expertise of orthopedic surgeons or radiologists, which poses challenges in resource-limited settings. To address this, the project aims to streamline the fracture detection process by integrating machine learning algorithms with digital image processing methods.

The initial phase involves acquiring X-ray images of the targeted body sections, showcasing both normal and damaged bones. These images are then categorized within the dataset based on the presence or absence of fractures. Utilizing this classified dataset, the performance of the automatic fracture detection system is both trained and evaluated.

Edge detection techniques serve as the initial step in the image processing pipeline for X-ray images, aiming to locate and highlight the contours of structures. The Canny edge detection algorithm is preferred among various methods due to its proficiency in capturing significant edges while minimizing noise. By delineating edges, we can pinpoint bone structures and potential fractures with greater accuracy, which is vital for the subsequent stages of processing.

Following edge detection, the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) method is employed to extract distinctive features from X-ray images. HOG is a widely used technique in computer vision for object recognition, particularly effective when the texture and shape of an object are critical for classification. By analyzing the distribution of gradients within specific regions of the image, HOG generates feature descriptors that represent the bone's structure and potential fracture patterns.

Once the features are extracted, a combination of machine learning classifiers, including Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM), is employed for the identification and classification of fractures. These classifiers are trained using the extracted features and corresponding labels from the dataset to discern patterns indicative of normal and fractured bone structures. Additionally, transfer learning techniques are applied to enhance classification accuracy, especially in scenarios with limited training data, by leveraging pre-trained deep learning models such as ResNet50.

Data augmentation techniques, such as horizontal flipping, are employed to enhance the diversity of the training dataset, ensuring the robustness and generalizability of the resulting model. These techniques support the model in learning invariant features and adapting to variations in X-ray images captured under different conditions. Furthermore, the model's proficiency in detecting and classifying fractures is evaluated using standard metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve.

The proposed method streamlines the process of detecting and classifying fractures in X-ray images by integrating machine learning algorithms with digital image processing techniques. Utilizing edge detection, feature extraction, and machine learning classifiers, this system has shown promising results in accurately identifying fractures across different body parts. Future research could aim to enhance patient care and outcomes by refining the model's architecture, fine-tuning hyperparameters, and exploring its real-time implementation in clinical environments.

Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) play a pivotal role in medical imaging studies, particularly in automating the detection and classification of fractures in X-ray images of the shoulder, elbow, and hand. A CNN's architecture typically comprises layers such as convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers. These layers collaborate to enable the network to discern intricate patterns and spatial correlations within the input images.

To ensure uniformity across all images for seamless integration into the CNN architecture, raw X-ray images are preprocessed and resized to a consistent input size prior to their use in the project's CNNs. Leveraging widely-recognized pre-trained models like ResNet50 or VGG16 gives the CNNs a head start with feature extraction capabilities honed through pre-training on large datasets such as ImageNet. The pre-trained CNN

model undergoes fine-tuning on the target X-ray image dataset through transfer learning, enabling it to retain the high-level features from ImageNet while adjusting to the specific features crucial for diagnosing fractures.

By employing gradient descent and backpropagation, the enhanced CNN model is trained to distinguish between fractured and normal bone structures in X-ray images. Furthermore, the model's efficacy is evaluated using an independent test dataset, focusing on performance metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and the area under the ROC curve. This study demonstrates the use of CNNs for the reliable and accurate detection of fractures, providing clinicians with a valuable tool for the swift diagnosis of bone injuries.

Additionally, the project employs a range of strategies to bolster the performance and generalization of the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) in use. Data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, zooming, and horizontal flipping, artificially expand the training dataset's diversity, mitigating overfitting and boosting the model's ability to generalize across new data. Concurrently, dropout regularization is implemented during training to prevent co-adaptation of neurons and further diminish overfitting risks. These methodologies ensure that the CNN models are robust and adept at detecting fractures across diverse X-ray images, even amidst noise or variations in imaging conditions.

To enhance model performance, the architecture and hyperparameters of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are meticulously fine-tuned through systematic experimentation. Parameters such as learning rate, batch size, and the number of convolutional layers are calibrated using techniques like grid search or random search to discover the optimal setup for the specific task. Hyperparameter optimization is crucial for achieving cutting-edge results in fracture detection and for refining CNN performance. The project demonstrates the potential of deep learning methods in automating medical image analysis by rigorously developing and training CNN models, paving the way for more precise and efficient diagnostic processes in clinical environments.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Fracture prediction by importing the necessary Python libraries and the dataset

```
import os
from tkinter import filedialog
import customtkinter as ctk
import pyautogui
import pygetwindow
from PIL import ImageTk, Image
from predictions import predict
```

The provided code initializes a graphical user interface (GUI) program designed for the detection of bone fractures. It structures the layout with frames and sets the title and dimensions of the main window. The GUI is equipped with buttons and labels to facilitate user interaction and display information. By clicking the "Upload Image" button, users can navigate a file dialog window to upload an X-ray image.

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Once uploaded, the GUI exhibits the selected image. Upon clicking the "Predict" button, the program invokes the predict_gui() function, which in turn passes the filename of the uploaded image to the predict function within the predictions module for analysis.

Subsequently, the prediction result is displayed on the GUI, revealing if the bone is fractured or intact. Users can save a screenshot of this result by choosing the "Save Result" option, which prompts them to pick a save location and filename. The application captures the relevant result section, crops it to display only the prediction result, and saves it as an image file in the chosen directory. Additionally, clicking the information button will display a window containing instructions for using the bone fracture detection system.

V. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the efficacy of an automated fracture detection system that integrates machine learning with digital image processing techniques. The system adeptly extracts and analyzes critical image features that signify fractures in X-ray images, utilizing edge detection algorithms such as the Canny method and feature extraction techniques like the Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG). Employing machine learning classifiers including Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Support Vector Machine (SVM), the model achieves precise and rapid diagnosis by categorizing X-ray images into fractured and non-fractured categories. The findings underscore the potential of our automated fracture detection model to enhance diagnostic precision and accessibility, particularly in regions where professional medical expertise is scarce.

Future research should focus on improving the proposed model's functionality and applicability in clinical environments. Additionally, exploring ways to integrate this automated system into existing healthcare workflows could improve patient outcomes by optimizing diagnostic processes. By addressing ongoing challenges in fracture diagnosis and

management, this technology holds the promise to revolutionize medical imaging practices and significantly advance the delivery of more effective and efficient healthcare worldwide.

Moreover, the efficacy of the automatic fracture detection system underscores the transformative potential of artificial intelligence in healthcare. By leveraging advanced computational tools, medical professionals can enhance their diagnostic skills and overcome existing challenges in fracture detection. This research represents a significant advancement in the development of smart medical imaging technologies, which will assist physicians in promptly and precisely identifying patients, thereby enhancing patient care and the efficiency of healthcare services.

In conclusion, integrating machine learning algorithms with digital image processing offers a promising solution for addressing the complexities of diagnosing fractures from X-ray images. As technology continues to progress, advancements in this field have the potential to transform medical diagnostics and alter the landscape of healthcare. Leveraging the opportunities afforded by artificial intelligence, we can equip medical practitioners with powerful tools to improve patient care and bolster public health outcomes.

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